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Characterization and sequence analyses of hyper-cellulase producing *Bacillus paramycoides*

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ABSTRACT

The present study was investigated to isolate and identify a hyper-cellulase producing bacterium from soil. Initially, a total of 11 cellulase producing bacteria were isolated from the collected soil sample using serial dilution technique, followed by cellulose hydrolysis plate assay method. The hyper-cellulase producing bacterium was identified as *Bacillus paramycoides* strain KASHA using different biochemical and molecular characterization tools. Furthermore, 16S rRNA sequences of strain KASHA were used to determine the secondary structure of RNA using RNAfold web server. As per the results obtained, the minimum free energy value for strain KASHA was calculated as -199.69 kcal/mol. Mountain plot and entropy depicted the hierarchical representation of RNA secondary structure. The GC content of sequence for strain KASHA was calculated as 53%. The evolutionary relationship of the strain was determined using Neighbor Joining algorithm which showed close resemblance with other bacilli strains.

Keywords: Cellulase, Characterization, *Bacillus paramycoides*, Phylogenetic tree, 16S rRNA sequencing

1. INTRODUCTION

Soil is a dynamic and biologically rich environment that harbours a wide range of microorganisms, including bacteria, fungi, actinomycetes, and protozoa. These soil microflorae

play crucial roles in various ecological processes such as organic matter decomposition, nitrogen fixation, soil fertility enhancement, and the production of valuable secondary metabolites [1]. Among them, bacteria are the most dominant and diverse group due to their metabolic versatility and physiological adaptability. They not only support nutrient cycling and soil health but also serve as a vast reservoir of industrially important enzymes [2].

Enzymes produced by soil bacteria function as biocatalysts. Compared to chemical catalysts and other microbial enzymes, bacterial enzymes are more stable, eco-friendly, and efficient, especially under extreme conditions. This makes them suitable for a wide range of industrial applications [3, 4]. One such group of enzymes that has garnered significant attention is cellulases, known for their role in breaking down cellulose.

Cellulases (E.C.3.2.1.4) are a group of hydrolytic enzymes that convert lignocellulosic biomass into fermentable sugars. These enzymes include endoglucanases, exoglucanases, and β -glucosidases, which work synergistically to depolymerize cellulose into glucose [5]. Due to their diverse applications, cellulases are among the top three commercially used hydrolytic enzymes globally [6]. They are extensively utilized in various sectors, including biofuel production, textile processing, food and feed industries, detergents, paper and pulp industries, and waste management [7, 8].

Bacterial cellulases, in particular, are produced by various bacterial genera. These bacteria offer advantages such as fast growth, ease of genetic manipulation, and the ability to produce enzymes with specific industrially desirable traits [9, 10]. Despite ongoing research in cellulase production, the global demand for cellulases continues to grow, especially for several technological purposes. Therefore, there is an urgent need to explore diverse and less explored environments to isolate novel hyper cellulolytic bacterial strain. This study was designed to isolate a potent hyper cellulase producing bacterium from soil and characterize it through morphological, biochemical, molecular, and bioinformatics techniques.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Sample collection

Fig. 1. Map, location, and co-ordinates of soil sample collection site.

Soil sample was collected from the campus of Hindustan College of Arts & Science, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India. Map, location, and co-ordinates of soil sample collection site is shown in Fig. 1. The collected sample was brought in the laboratory in sterile polythene zip lock pouch.

2. 2. Isolation of cellulase producing bacteria

Cellulase producing bacteria were isolated from the collected soil sample using serial dilution technique on sterilized Nutrient agar medium containing 0.5% (w/v) carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC). After spreading the suspension using L-rod, plates were incubated at 37 °C in incubator for 24 h under aerobic condition. After required period of incubation, the appearance of different colonies on the agar plates was observed and purified.

2. 3. Extracellular cellulase production

All the isolates were observed for the production of extracellular cellulase. Isolates were cultured in the sterilized Nutrient broth medium consisting of 0.5% (w/v) CMC and incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. The culture was further centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 15 min for collecting the supernatant. Alongside, CMC agar media (g/L: CMC – 5.0; agar – 20.0; and pH – 7.0) were prepared for agar well diffusion assay. The supernatant (100 µL) was poured into the well created and incubated up to 24 h at 37 °C. Further, the CMC agar plate was flooded with Lugol's iodine solution and observed for clear zone of CMC hydrolysis [10].

2. 4. Identification of hyper-cellulase producing bacterium

2. 4. 1. Morphological and biochemical properties

The morphological and biochemical properties of potent bacterium exhibiting hyper-cellulase production (based on zone of hydrolysis) were carried out using standard Bergey's Manual of Systemic Bacteriology [11]. Biochemical tests viz. indole, methyl red, voges-proskauer (VP), citrate utilization, urease, oxidase, and catalase were performed aseptically using standard protocols.

2. 4. 2. Molecular characterization

Genomic DNA of the bacteria was isolated using NucleoSpin® DNA isolation kit (Macherey-Nagel) following manufacturer's instructions. Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) amplification was carried out in a PCR thermal cycler (Model - GeneAmp PCR System 9700, Applied Biosystems). The PCR product was loaded in 1.2% (w/v) agarose gel prepared in 0.5X TBE buffer containing 0.5 µg/mL ethidium bromide. The gel was visualized in UV transilluminator and the image was captured under UV light using gel documentation system.

2. 5. Sequence analyses using bioinformatics tools

2. 5. 1. BLAST and GenBank submission

The 16S rRNA sequences of bacteria were submitted to Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST), National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi>) for similarity search. The strain was deposited to

GenBank, NCBI (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/submit/>) and accession number was assigned for the isolate.

3. 5. 2. Thermodynamic structure prediction

The minimum free energy (MFE), mountain plot, and entropy of sequences were determined using RNAfold web server [12]. Temperature was set at 37°C for evaluating the stability of chemical or biological molecules or entities of the isolate.

3. 5. 3. Determination of Guanine Cytosine (GC) content

The GC content of the sequences was calculated according to the algorithm of Rosano and Ceccarelli [13]. The GC content (%) was calculated as:

$$\text{GC content (\%)} = \frac{\text{Total number of G and C}}{\text{Total number of A, T, C, and G}} \times 100$$

3. 5. 4. Open reading frame (ORF) determination

The ORF of sequences of strain was determined using ORF Finder (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/orffinder/>).

3. 5. 5. Phylogenetic tree construction

The evolutionary relationship of the strain was inferred by comparison with the 16S rRNA sequences of close isolates. Bootstrap tree was inferred using Neighbor Joining (NJ) algorithm in MEGA software version 11.0 [14].

3. RESULTS

3. 1. Isolation of cellulase producing bacteria

A total of 11 cellulase-producing bacterial cultures were isolated. Among those bacterial cultures, isolate 2 showed maximum zone of CMC hydrolysis. Other isolates showed comparatively lower cellulase production (Figure not shown).

3. 2. Identification of hyper-cellulase producing bacterium

Since, isolate 2 was reported as prominent producer of extracellular cellulase, hence this very isolate was selected further for the identification based on morphological, biochemical, molecular, and various bioinformatics techniques. Isolate 2 showed cream white, large, smooth, and round shaped colony appearance on Nutrient agar medium.

The isolate exhibited positive results for VP, citrate utilization, catalase, and oxidase tests. On the other hand, negative results for indole, methyl red, and urease tests were observed. After performing Gram staining and endospore staining, the isolate was observed as Gram positive endospore producing bacterium (Fig. 2).

The amplicon of ~1500 bp was observed in gel documentation system (Figure not shown). The isolate was further identified as *Bacillus paramycoides* strain KASHA (Accession no.-OR673970) after 16S rRNA sequencing.

Fig. 2. Morphological and biochemical tests results of isolate 2.

3. 3. Sequence analyses using bioinformatics tools

The 16S rRNA sequences of strain KASHA were used to determine the secondary structure of RNA using RNAfold web server. The thermodynamic parameter i.e. MFE for strain KASHA was calculated as -199.69 kcal/mol (Fig. 3a). Mountain plot and entropy depicted the hierarchical representation of RNA secondary structure (Fig. 3b).

Further, the GC content of sequence for strain KASHA was calculated as 53% (Fig. 3c). Fig. 3d shows 1 ORF region for the strain.

The evolutionary relationship of the strain was determined using NJ method which showed close resemblance with other bacilli strains (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3. (a) RNA secondary structure prediction, (b) Mountain plot graph, (c) GC content determination, and (d) ORF determination of strain KASHA.

Fig. 4. Phylogenetic tree construction of *B. paramycoides* strain KASHA.

4. DISCUSSION

Numerous studies have been conducted to explore microbial communities residing in different soil types across varied geographic locations. Soil is a highly dynamic and biologically

active ecosystem that harbours a vast array of microorganisms, among which bacteria are the most dominant [4]. These bacteria play fundamental roles in sustaining essential ecological processes, such as nutrient cycling, organic matter decomposition, and soil detoxification [15].

Beyond the ecological significance, soil bacteria are gaining attention in various industrial sectors, including the food, pharmaceutical, agricultural, and biofuel industries, primarily due to their ability to produce a range of valuable enzymes [16-18].

Among these enzymes, cellulases are particularly important because of their role in biotechnological industries. To meet the growing industrial demand, it is vital to isolate and characterize hyper-cellulase producing bacterial strains that possess enhanced enzymatic properties. In the present investigation, 11 bacterial isolates were screened for cellulase production, and among them, *B. paramycoides* strain KASHA emerged as the most potent producer of extracellular cellulase.

This observation is in agreement with prior research, which also reported cellulase production by *B. paramycoides* [19], indicating its potential as a robust cellulolytic bacterium. Modern bacterial taxonomy heavily relies on molecular techniques with 16S rRNA gene sequencing serving as a standard tool for accurate identification and classification [20-22].

The 16S rRNA gene is highly conserved across bacterial species, yet it contains hypervariable regions that allow differentiation at the genus and species levels [23, 24].

In this study, molecular analysis of 16S rRNA gene of strain KASHA was carried out using bioinformatics tools to determine its phylogenetic position and genetic characteristics. Various computational analyses, including RNA secondary structure prediction, thermodynamic parameter estimation, ORF identification, GC content analysis, and phylogenetic tree construction were employed in this study. The RNA secondary structure was predicted using MFE calculations, revealing a stable folding pattern indicative of structural integrity [25].

Mountain plots and entropy graphs provided insight into the hierarchical structure and stability of RNA regions, with helices represented as rising mountains and loops as peaks. The GC content of the gene was found to be above 50%, suggesting greater stability of the RNA structure.

Additionally, ORF analysis identified potential protein-coding regions, further supporting the functional viability of the gene. The phylogenetic tree showed that strain KASHA closely aligns with other *Bacillus* species, confirming its taxonomic identity. These comprehensive molecular and bioinformatic characterizations affirm the strain's potential for industrial cellulase production and open new avenues for its application in various biotechnological sectors.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In summary, a total of 11 cellulolytic bacteria were isolated from soil. The isolate estimating maximum production of cellulase was identified as *B. paramycoides* strain KASHA based on morphological, biochemical, and molecular characterization tools.

Further, the determination of RNA secondary structure, thermodynamics parameters, ORF regions, GC content, and phylogenetic tree construction using 16S rRNA sequences classified the isolates among particular bacterial species. Findings suggested prominent role of *B. paramycoides* strain KASHA as ideal cellulase producer in future.

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